

COMPONENTS OF CREATIVITY MANIFESTED ON THE BASIS OF DIVERSIFICATION PRINCIPLES

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The task of unveiling a student's creative potential is intimately linked with the task of identifying the main structural components of creativity in education and studying the conditions of their manifestation.

Creativity in the field of education is directly related to the initial formation of a teacher's pedagogical skills and includes a range of components

(Table 1)

Creativity and Its Main Components.

	Kreativlik komponentlari	Xususiyati	Namoyon bo'lish sharoiti
1	Intellectual knowledge	Mastery of knowledge, skills, and competencies in one's area of specialization.	Involvement in all aspects of educational activities.
2	Non-conformism	Avoiding common stereotypes and maintaining an independent stance.	Handling challenging and unconventional scenarios.
3	Motivation and emotional curiosity	Active participation in discussions and communication.	Engaging in lessons that emphasize interaction and communication.
4	Originality	Personal perspective in solving problems and uniqueness in thought.	In all types of communication.
5	Abstracting	Rapid comprehension and clear expression of problems.	Discussing and resolving educational challenges.
6	Metaphoricity	Readiness to work in different contexts, using symbolic representations.	Articulating the characteristics of

			the subject matter
7	Adaptability	Quick identification of unique details in a problem, swift transition between ideas.	Navigating and debating complex and unique situations.
8	Generativity	Abundance of thoughts, ideas, and proposals.	Again emphasizing the importance of communication in all forms.
9	Emotional-psychological components	Desire and positive emotions in solving problems, satisfaction from success, and dissatisfaction from unmet objectives.	Applying these skills in the resolution of specific problems.

The components of creativity mentioned above, as the inner potential of a student, require a certain pedagogical and educational environment, as well as didactic conditions, to manifest in practical situations. The emergence of such an environment and didactic conditions is considered crucial in the educational process, with a focus on achieving the predominance of general didactic principles of diversification. By defining the impact of diversification principles, which encompass the organization and management of education, as well as material-technical and methodological support, on the student's learning and cognitive activities through general criteria, we delve into the significance of general didactic principles in revealing the creative potential of the learner (in our case, the student).

In the previous chapter of our research, we extensively discussed the effects of the general didactic principles of diversification on the development of the learner's personality in the educational process. We present the importance of these principles in revealing the distinct components of a student's creativity through Table 2.4.

Table 2

Components of Creativity Manifested on the Basis of Diversification Principles

General Didactic Principles of Diversification	Characteristic of the Principle	Most Prominent Components of Creativity	Secondary Manifesting Components
1. Principle of Continuous Variability	The principle of continuous variability is reflected in the constant motion of the education system, with changes directed towards satisfying the interests of the learner.	Creates conditions for the manifestation of components such as intellectual knowledge, adaptability, motivation, abstraction, and generativity.	Other components also manifest to a certain extent.
2. Principle of Individual Orientation	This implies the necessity of considering the educational needs of each individual without overlooking them.	Components like anticonformism, motivation, emotional-psychological aspects, metaphors, and originality are more prominently manifested.	Manifestation of components such as intellectual, originality, adaptability.
3. Principle of Alternative Variability	Learners can choose an educational process that suits their aspirations and educational trajectory from diverse, multifaceted, and multi-level forms of education.	Intellectual, generativity, motivation and emotional curiosity, originality, adaptability.	Emotional-psychological components, abstraction, metaphorical aspects.

4. Principle of Humanism and Innovation	Factors influencing societal development include economic-societal, spiritual-educational, and cultural characteristics.	Generativity, anticonformism, emotional-psychological components, abstraction, adaptability.	An environment is formed for the manifestation of other components.
5. Principle of Democracy and Freedom	It signifies the equal rights of the learner and the teacher, with both being considered subjects performing their respective functions.	All components of creativity are manifested in a way that complements and develops each other.	All components.

It should be noted that assessing the level of creativity of students as future professionals, consequently, involves studying creativity criteria separately. This can lead to determining the degree to which the primary components of creativity, as shown in Table 2.1.1, are manifested in the learner, and can be taken as a criterion for the methodology of eliciting creativity.

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